

Impact of Geometric Variation on the Performance of Cold Formed Bearings

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Research Background

- 3.5 year project working with a leading bearing manufacturer to:
 - Map the design and manufacturing processes used in the production of self-lubricating plain spherical bearings
 - Statistically characterise bearing material properties and processing parameters
 - Simulate the manufacturing process using validated models
 - Provide design tools for future bearing introduction

✦ Elements of Plain Spherical Bearings

🔥 Applications

🍁 The Nosing Process

Bearing Assembly
before Double Nosing

Bearing Assembly
after Double Nosing

🍁 The Nosing Process (cont'd)

Current Issues

- Production dominated by:
 - Past experience (limited design for production data)
 - Trial and error process settings
 - Many test batches
 - Typically 30-50% loss per batch
- Manufacturing variations impact on:
 - Geometric conformity (specification requirement)
 - Frictional moment (customer performance measure)

Robust tolerances desired for waste reduction, cost effectiveness, performance and compatibility

🔥 In-Process Failure Modes

TIPPING	OPEN MOUTH	CHURCH WINDOW	LINER SLIPPAGE	OFFSET
SATURNISATION	BALL CRUSHING	NECKING	STICKING	

🍁 Failure Mode Importance

✦ Nosing Process Inputs and Outputs

Methodology

- Measure 32 bearing sleeve dimensions (i.e. chamfer outer and inner diameter, angle and geometric length) prior to the nosing process
- Record nosing process outputs (i.e. forming load and frictional moment) of all bearings
- Statistically analyse the data to assess whether there is a statistical significance between the key features of either side of the bearing outer race
- Calculate process capability indices, and provide recommendations as to process performance

🔥 Chamfer Concentricity Issues

🔥 Schematic of Chamfer Tolerance Limits

✦ Sensitivity of Forming Load to Variation in Chamfer Angle and Length

🔥 Sleeve Engineering Drawing and Measurement Points

🌿 Sleeve Measurements using an Optical Comparator

🌿 Sleeve Volume Distribution

✦ Shift in Chamfer Concentricity (absolute values in x-y plane)

Shift in Chamfer Concentricity using Normal and Folded Normal Distributions

Other Sleeve Measurement Results

🌿 Impact on Forming Load

🌿 Distribution of Frictional Moment

Conclusions

- Analytical approaches not available for assessing the impact of feature variation in cold forming processes
- Large sample size empirical studies and FE simulations are required for such studies to have confidence
- Extremes in chamfer eccentricity in particular have a direct impact on many in-process failure modes and variation in bearing frictional moment and process forming load
- Recommendation to the industrial collaborator is that geometric tolerances be introduced on engineering drawings for chamfers in addition to sleeve diameters
- A change in machining process set-up may also be required to realise process capability levels and reduce failure rates

Future Work

- Conduct process capability analyses for sleeve chamfer features across a range of bearing sizes
- Experimentally model the friction during nosing (indications are that it is non-linear)
- Develop stochastic FE models using Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS)
- Create sensitivity measures for all nosing parameters and develop robust tolerance settings
- Further neutron diffraction testing to study stress patterns due to over-forming

Thank you for listening!

Any questions?